

Співставлення даних з зовнішньої торгівлі між Польщею, Словаччиною та Україною

У статті розглянуто питання пов'язані з експортом–імпортом товарів між Україною та Польщею і Словаччиною, а саме: загальна структура експорту та імпорту за конкретними товарними групами та співставлення даних торгівлі за методом дзеркальної статистики.

Проведено аналіз основних показників: розходження між експортом та імпортом товарів у відповідних базах даних.

Доведено залежність між правильною реєстрацією та обліком товарів на митницях для подальшого аналізу даних по взаємній торгівлі.

Ключові слова: зовнішня торгівля, експорт, імпорт, товари, ЄАВТ, розходження, співставлення, товарна група, УКТЗЕД.

ШЕМЧУК М.Ю.

Сопоставление данных по внешней торговле между Польшей, Словакией и Украиной

В статье рассмотрены вопросы связанные с экспортом–импортом товаров между Украиной и Польшей и Словакией, а именно: общая структура экспорта и импорта по конкретным товарным группам и сопоставления данных торговли по методу зеркальной статистики.

Проведен анализ основных показателей: различия между экспортом и импортом товаров в соответствующих базах данных.

Доказана зависимость между правильной регистрацией и учетом товаров на таможенных для дальнейшего анализа данных взаимной торговли.

Ключевые слова: внешняя торговля, экспорт, импорт, товары, ЕАСТ, расхождения, сопоставления, товарная группа, УКТВЕД.

SHEMCHUK M.Y.

Comparison of foreign trade data between Poland, Slovakia and Ukraine

The article deals with issues related to export–import of goods between Poland, Slovakia and Ukraine, namely: general structure of export and import by specific product groups and comparison of trade data by the method of mirror statistics.

The main indicators were analyzed: the difference between export and import of goods in the respective databases.

The correlation between proper registration and registration of goods at customs for further analysis of mutual trade data is proved.

Keywords: foreign trade, export, import, goods, difference, comparison, commodity group, UKTZED.

Objective. The main purpose of the study is to study statistically the differences between Ukraine's foreign trade in goods with Poland and Slovakia.

Based on the goal, the following tasks are set in the work:

- 1) to analyze the general situation in trade of goods between Ukraine and the neighboring countries;
- 2) assess differences in foreign trade in goods between the countries studied;

3) to find out the reasons for such discrepancies and to make recommendations for their elimination.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. This topic is not well covered in scientific publications. That is why it is advisable to use the methodologies of the State Statistics Service and data of international databases, in particular, data on the volume of foreign trade operations of other countries are taken from the UN Comtrade database.

Background. Modern statistics have developed and used many different methods to analyze and collate data that can be used in completely different fields. In the context of global globalization and the interaction of the countries of the world with each other, the question of comparability of statistics remains one of the most important in the statistics of international trade.

The analysis of foreign trade statistics data makes it possible to identify the causes of data discrepancies that result from the action of many factors. The main of these, in practice, are: mismatch of geographical, economic and statistical territories of the state; accounting for foreign trade in goods by different systems: general or special system of trade; the difference in the methodology of collecting and customs clearance of goods; inconsistency of indication of the trading country, country of origin or country of departure in customs declarations when transporting goods [5].

One of the methods for studying the harmonization of foreign trade statistics is the method of mirror statistics. This method implies consistency, comparison of import of goods of one particular country with the corresponding export of goods of the partner country [5]. Using the method of mirror statistics in practice, it is advisable to consider the example of comparing foreign trade in goods between Ukraine and neighboring countries: Poland and Slovakia. [7].

In foreign trade in goods the goods are classified according to the Ukrainian Classification of Goods of Foreign Economic Activity (hereinafter referred to as UKTZED).

In general, the discrepancy in the accounting of goods is a consequence of the influence of many

factors, the main ones being the methodological differences in the accounting of goods (the use of different classifications of goods, the difference in exchange rates), interrupted transit, the presence at the legislative level of certain preferences or, conversely, additional customs fees, avoidance of declaration goods, incorrect definition in the customs declaration of the counterparty country, errors in the collection and processing of data.

Today, Poland is the main partner of Ukraine in trade in goods for export, this is due to the fact that Poland and Ukraine have a common border and old established active operations for the purchase and sale of goods. The basic document of such cooperation is the Agreement between Ukraine and the Republic of Poland on good neighborliness, friendly relations and cooperation of May 18, 1992, which establishes mutual obligations regarding the development of relations in the spirit of friendship, cooperation, mutual respect, trust and good neighborliness on the basis of international law.

Over the past 6 years, Ukrainian exports to Poland increased by 7.3% on average per year. Also, compared with 2013, exports in 2018 increased by 27.8%, while imports decreased by 10.6%.

Discrepancies in the data on foreign trade in goods between Ukraine and Poland are presented in Table 1.

In general, we can say that the discrepancy in the amount of goods that Ukraine receives from Poland is 30.8%. The main reason for these discrepancies is the inaccuracy and errors in determining the partner country, the trading country and the country of destination of goods, as well as the difference in the methodology for collecting data on statistics on foreign trade in goods.

Table 1. Differences in export of goods from Poland to Ukraine

Commodity code and title by Ukrainian Classification of Commodities in Foreign Trade	Export of Poland	Import of Ukraine	Divergence	
			thsd. USD	%
Total	5 249 278,3	3 634 616,8	1 614 661,5	30,8
of which				
27 mineral fuel, petroleum and petroleum distillation products	105 811,1	303 413,8	-197 602,7	-186,8
39 plastics and polymeric materials	399 961,4	318 175,6	81 785,8	20,4
48 paper, paperboard	147 760,2	112 382,0	35 378,2	23,9
84 nuclear reactors, boilers, machines	617 346,8	296 732,6	320 614,2	51,9
85 electric machines	444 734,8	313 540,1	131 194,7	29,5
87 ground transport facilities excluding railway	446 097,7	284 477,3	161 620,4	36,2

Source: author's own calculations for the data [2], [4].

СТАТИСТИКА ВИДІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ТА ПІДПРИЄМСТВ В УКРАЇНІ

The largest discrepancies are observed in the group of mineral fuels (Poland receives 1.9 times more than noted by Ukraine), and means of land transport, except for rail (Poland receives 36.2% more than Ukraine sends).

At the same time, total exports of Ukraine differ from Polish imports by 8.7%. General discrepancies by product groups are presented in Table 2

The largest discrepancies can be observed in the group of goods that Poland receives from Ukraine: electric cars (66.1%) and fats and oils of animal or vegetable origin (20.0%), i.e. Poland sent more goods to Ukraine than noted in the import of our country.

These discrepancies are explained by an incorrect definition in the customs declarations of the counterparty country and errors in the determination of goods when filling out the declaration.

In general, in recent years, Ukraine has steadily increased cooperation with Poland.

Another fairly significant trading partner of Ukraine in Europe is Slovakia.

Economic cooperation with Slovakia is based on Double Taxation Treaties (January 1997), mutual employment of citizens (February 1998), as well as cooperation in the field of mechanical engineering, the military–industrial complex, trade, science and technology. Economic cooperation between the two countries accelerated when negative trends were overcome regarding a decrease in the volume of trade: Slovakia entered the group of countries with the largest exports of Ukraine.

Over the past 6 years, Ukrainian exports to Slovakia increased by 5.1% on average per year. Also,

Table 2. Differences in export of goods from Ukraine to Poland

Commodity code and title by Ukrainian Classification of Commodities in Foreign Trade	Export of Ukraine	Import of Poland	Divergence	
			thsd. USD	%
Total	3 257 581,0	2 973 524,2	284 056,8	8,7
of which				
III.15 Animal or plant fats and oils	126 526,7	151 860,7	-25 334,1	-20,0
23 remains and wastes of food industry	105 533,0	111 394,5	-5 861,6	-5,6
26 ores, slags, ashes	383 018,5	406 864,2	-23 845,7	-6,2
27 mineral fuel, petroleum and petroleum distillation products	98 009,0	92 185,0	5 824,0	5,9
44 wood and articles of wood	267 451,6	299 609,8	-32 158,2	-12,0
72 ferrous metals	484 779,2	511 577,3	-26 798,1	-5,5
73 preparations from ferrous metals	126 844,6	136 594,4	-9 749,9	-7,7
85 electric machines	376 876,1	127 670,8	249 205,3	66,1
94 furniture	225 788,4	112 094,9	113 693,5	50,4

Source: author's own calculations for the data [2], [4].

Table 3. Differences in export of goods from Slovakia to Ukraine

Commodity code and title by Ukrainian Classification of Commodities in Foreign Trade	Export of Slovakia	Import of Ukraine	Divergence	
			thsd. USD	%
Total	488 024,6	525 655,5	-37 631,0	-7,7
of which				
25 salt, sulphur, soil and stones	39 071,4	36 538,8	2 532,6	6,5
27 mineral fuel, petroleum and petroleum distillation products	4 550,0	25 504,4	-20 954,5	-460,5
39 plastics and polymeric materials	39 259,8	39 333,0	-73,2	-0,2
40 rubber and articles of rubber	22 824,9	21 459,5	1 365,4	6,0
48 paper, paperboard	24 991,6	23 019,0	1 972,5	7,9
72 ferrous metals	55 007,4	58 169,0	-3 161,5	-5,7
84 nuclear reactors, boilers, machines	60 935,9	60 132,8	803,1	1,3
85 electric machines	30 483,2	19 483,2	11 000,0	36,1
87 ground transport facilities excluding railway	63 406,4	118 641,5	-55 235,2	-87,1

Source: author's own calculations for the data [2], [4].

Table 4. Differences in export of goods from Ukraine to Slovakia

Commodity code and title by Ukrainian Classification of Commodities in Foreign Trade	Export of Ukraine	Import of Slovakia	Divergence	
			thsd. USD	%
Total	864 150,0	764 921,3	99 228,7	11,5
of which				
02 meat and meat preparations	59 951,6	21 175,8	38 775,8	64,7
26 ores, slags, ashes	337 360,5	358 007,7	-20 647,3	-6,1
29 organic chemical combinations	71 685,5	4 085,8	67 599,7	94,3
44 wood and articles of wood	36 915,9	38 588,8	-1 672,8	-4,5
72 ferrous metals	55 032,9	64 082,2	-9 049,3	-16,4
84 nuclear reactors, boilers, machines	27 667,8	27 849,4	-181,6	-0,7
85 electric machines	147 912,8	131 135,4	16 777,4	11,3

Source: author's own calculations for the data [2], [4].

compared with 2013, exports in 2018 increased by 14.8% while imports decreased by 20.8%.

The results of comparing trade data between Ukraine and Slovakia are presented in table 3.

The results show that the discrepancies in foreign trade in goods between Ukraine and Slovakia are significant. In general, the discrepancy between Slovak exports and Ukrainian imports is 7.7%.

In particular, Slovakia sends 4.6 times more mineral fuels to Ukraine than Ukrainian statistics shows, and Ukraine receives 36.1% more electric cars from Slovakia than Slovak statistics.

These discrepancies are explained by the incorrect definition of the counterparty country when registering goods at customs, as well as due to the fact that goods can be sold during transit from one country to another.

The results of the return journey of goods from Ukraine to Slovakia are presented in table 4

Based on the calculation results, it can be concluded that Ukraine exports to Slovakia 11.5% more goods than Slovakia officially receives.

The largest discrepancies in 93.4% are observed in the group of organic chemical compounds. Slovakia imports meat and edible meat from Ukraine by 64.7% more than the official export of Ukraine.

This is primarily due to the scattered structure of foreign trade in goods between Ukraine and Slovakia and the different classification of goods.

Conclusion

Comparison of data between the partner countries and Ukraine according to the method of mirror statistics shows that the main discrepancies in the data of export and import of goods between countries are associated with methodological dif-

ferences, errors in filling out customs declarations, incorrect determination of the country of origin and destination of goods at customs and not taking into account the official statistics of the shadow sector of the economy.

One of the main problems during customs clearance is corruption. To solve this problem, it would be rational to translate the entire customs robot into electronic form and into a single database. This would speed up the work of customs, since during check of goods and scanning of a bar code through a single database of customs declarations, all columns of declarations would be checked immediately.

There are also causes of disagreement that are much more difficult to resolve, such as differences due to confidentiality in the foreign trade statistics of the partner country. The only way out of this situation is to include data with the exception of confidential information, but by agreement between countries, which information should be considered confidential and not taken into account.

Another important way of avoiding disagreement is to create an effective system of interaction between importing enterprises, exporters with statistical authorities to check export volumes and destination countries. This will make the information more accurate, which will help the statistics authorities to work more effectively.

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ПАВЛЕНКО В.П.,
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Статистичний моніторинг стратегічно важливих підприємств в Україні

Предмет дослідження – особливості статистичного моніторингу стратегічно важливих підприємств для економіки та безпеки країни.

Метою написання **статті** є розгляд питань моніторингу стратегічно важливих для економіки та безпеки країни та визначення напрямів його вдосконалення для обґрунтування засобів державного регулювання.

Методологія проведення роботи – положення інституційної теорії, теорії управління, кейнсіанської концепції. На основі системного підходу з використанням методів аналізу та синтезу обґрунтована необхідність здійснення моніторингу стратегічно важливих для економіки та безпеки держави в економіці України.

Результати роботи – розглянуті питання визначення поняття та переліку стратегічно важливих підприємств в Україні та країнах світу, критерії їх ідентифікації; організації статистичного моніторингу функціонування зазначеного кола підприємств, наведено пропозиції щодо його відновлення в рамках моніторингу ефективності управління об'єктами державної власності з урахуванням актуалізації інформації, що отримується.

Висновки – важливою умовою забезпечення динамічного соціально-економічного розвитку країни є чітке визначення поняття «стратегічно важливі підприємства» та актуалізація їх переліку; проведення статистичного моніторингу різних аспектів їх фінансово-господарської діяльності та запровадження стосовно них комплексу заходів державного регулювання, перш за все, стосовно підвищення конкурентоспроможності національної економіки за рахунок активізації інноваційно-інвестиційної діяльності, що можливо в рамках моніторингу ефективності управління об'єктами державної власності, що здійснюється Мінекономіки України.

Ключові слова: стратегічно важливі підприємства для економіки й безпеки країни, моніторинг.